

FAQs

General

What is the RADx Data Hub?

The NIH Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics (RADx) Data Hub is a secure, cloud-based resource, designed to accelerate data-driven diagnostic innovation. It offers analytic tools and de-identified [RADx Initiative](#) data, so researchers can find studies of interest, and analyze curated and harmonized data with built-in tools.

Who can submit studies and data to the RADx Data Hub?

The RADx Data Hub accepts RADx programs' (RADx-UP, RADx-rad, RADx Tech, and RADx DHT) data. If you are not affiliated with these programs but would like to submit studies or data, please contact RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

Do I need to create a RADx Data Hub account?

You do not need to create a RADx Data Hub account to browse study information and view public documents (e.g., metadata files and data dictionaries).

To gain study-level access to original and transformed data files, you will need to create an account for the RADx Data Hub using your [eRA Commons](#) or [NIH Login](#) account. Once you have registered, sign into dbGaP with the same account and request access to a study. After you've been granted access, the study and its associated data files will appear in the **My Approved Data** tab where you can download them or transfer them to the **Analytics Workbench** for further analysis.

For more in-depth instructions on how to create an account for the RADx Data Hub, see the [tutorial](#).

To learn how to create an eRA Commons account, visit eRA's page on [how to register](#).

The NIH Login requires a smart card as opposed to a password. If you are having trouble with your smart card, visit the [RAS Login Help](#) page.

How do I change my password or profile information (e.g., forgot password, update profile information, email preferences, etc.)?

The RADx Data Hub does not manage passwords; it uses [eRA Commons](#) and [NIH Login](#) to authenticate researchers.

If you use eRA Commons, visit eRA's [forgot password page](#) to request a new password.

The NIH Login requires a smart card as opposed to a password. If you are having trouble with your smart card, visit the [RAS Login Help](#) page.

Can my account be deactivated?

Yes, the NIH will deactivate your account if you violate the [User Code of Conduct](#).

To deactivate your account, please contact the RADx Data Hub Administrator at RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

How do I get in contact with the Support team to report issues (such as bugs), suggest new features, or get questions answered?

There are two ways to get in contact with the RADx Support Team:

- Login and use the **Need Support?** button in the top navigation bar
- Email the [RADx Data Hub Support](#)

How do I ensure new team members can access the system?

The RADx Data Hub does not require an account to search studies and access publicly available information. If you are onboarding a new team member, they will need an [eRA account](#) or [NIH Login](#) to request study-level data file access in dbGaP. Once they have an account, they will need to register for the RADx Data Hub using the same account they use for dbGaP.

If you are offboarding a team member with an eRA account, contact the [eRA Help Desk](#).

If you are offboarding a team member with an NIH account, ensure they follow [NIH separation policies](#).

Data Organization in the RADx Data Hub

What kind of data are in the RADx Data Hub?

The RADx Data Hub is a centralized repository for in-progress and complete [RADx-UP](#), [RADx-rad](#), and [RADx Tech](#) research study data. It also hosts RADx DHT data information and links to the [RAPIDS platform](#). Research data includes curated and harmonized demographic, diagnostic, EHR, and digital health data to support analysis, diagnostic innovation, and public health preparedness.

What is the Global Codebook?

The NIH RADx Data Hub Global Codebook is the RADx-required Common Data Elements (CDEs) data dictionary. It contains precise mappings that organize (C)DCC-specific Data Elements into 12 unique, required CDE categories. Download the Global Codebook [here](#).

Requesting Access to Data within the RADx Data Hub

How do I find original data and transformed data files as well as data dictionaries, and metadata files?

Metadata files and data dictionary files are publicly available, so you can access them without logging in. You can find these files by navigating to the **Data Files** section of the **Study Overview** page for a study.

Harmonized and non-harmonized data files require study-level access from dbGaP. You must first request access to the study in dbGaP, and then it will appear in the My Approved Data page.

For more on finding these files, view the [RADx Tutorial](#) pages on:

- [Searching for Studies](#)
- [Viewing the Study Overview page](#)
- [Accessing 'My Approved Data'](#)

I want to use a RADx Data Hub study, but the data are not yet complete. How do I find out when the rest of the data will be available?

First, review the **RADx Content Updates** section toward the bottom of the **Home** page. This section contains links to recently received updated studies, and is updated every 90 days with information on:

- Newly registered studies
- Studies with updated files
- Studies with new files

If you can't find the study you are looking for, use the **Need Support?** button in the top navigation to ask our team about data availability.

Why do I need to apply for dbGaP study access in the RADx Data Hub?

The database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP) archives and distributes study results and provides mechanisms to control personal health-related study data access. The RADx Data Hub relies on these mechanisms to protect human subjects, supporting data use agreement compliance and granting access exclusively to trained researchers with Data Access Committee-approved research plans.

How do I request access to a study in dbGaP?

To request access to the data, click on the dbGaP link located under the **Study Name** on the **Study Overview** page. For more detailed instructions, review [Tips on a Successful Data Request](#).

Note: After obtaining dbGaP approval for RADx data, use the same eRA or NIH account used in dbGaP when logging into the RADx Data Hub.

How can I access older data file versions?

The My Approved Data page will only contain the current data file version. To receive an older version, please contact RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

I was approved for data through dbGaP, but I don't see it in my account. What should I do?

First, ensure that you are logged into the RADx Data Hub using the same NIH Login or eRA account you used when requesting access to the study in dbGaP and visit the **My Approved Data** page. If you still don't see what you are looking for, reach out to RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

Data Use and Compliance in the RADx Data Hub

What can I use to analyze data?

Researchers can use the RADx Data Hub in-browser analytics tools (Jupyter Notebooks or SAS Viya) or download the data into a CSV file for analysis.

Can I download data?

Yes, you can download data from either Sagemaker, SAS Viya, or your 'My Approved Data page'. Please see the [Workbench User Tutorial](#) for more details.

I'm having issues getting started with SageMaker and/or SAS Viya? Who can I contact?

Login and use the navigation bar's **Need Support?** button to submit **Workbench Support** questions or email us at RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

How do I request a larger compute instance?

Login and use the navigation bar's **Need Support?** button to submit **Workbench Support** questions or email us at RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

How do I request a SAS or Data Wrangler license?

In the RADx Data Hub:

1. Go to 'My Approved Data'
2. Select 'Apply for Add-ons' in the top-right
3. Fill out the required fields
4. Submit your request

How long can I use the data I obtained from the RADx Data Hub?

The RADx Data Hub relies on dbGaP to manage study and associated data file access. Requested dataset(s) access spans one (1) year with the option to renew for an additional year. You can renew access at the end of each calendar year; to learn how, review the dbGaP renewals Tutorial.

What should I put for the Cloud Use Statement and Cloud Service Provider Information in the Data Access Request if I plan to use the Researcher Workbench?

When preparing a **Cloud Use Statement** for a **Data Access Request (DAR)**, be sure to:

1. Indicate that you are planning to use the **RADx Data Hub Workbench** for data storage and analysis
2. Specify your **research focus area** and the **purpose**
3. Provide a brief description of how the **Workbench** will be utilized in your proposed research process
 - **Template**
 - I plan to use the RADx Data Hub Workbench to analyze **[your planned analysis]** using **[planned RADx data for analysis (and bring your own, if applicable)]**. Potential users for these cloud environments consist of the list of the 'Internal Collaborators' on this application and members of the external collaborator list attached to this application. External collaborators will submit their own dbGaP Data Access Requests.
 - **Example**
 - I plan to use the RADx Data Hub Workbench to analyze **the effectiveness of wastewater testing in predicting disease spread using RADx wastewater data and data from a non-RADx study (study or publication information and/or link)**. Potential users for these cloud environments consist of the list of the 'Internal Collaborators' on this application and members of the external collaborator list attached to this application. External collaborators will submit their own dbGaP Data Access Requests.

Are there restrictions or limitations to the use of data that are available in the RADx Data Hub?
RADx data are subject to the Data Use Certification Agreement you signed when you requested access to a study in dbGaP.

How long can I use the data I obtained from the RADx Data Hub?

The RADx Data Hub relies on dbGaP to manage access to studies and their associated data files. Requested dataset(s) access spans one (1) year with the option to renew for an additional year. You can renew your access at the end of each calendar year. To learn how to renew your access, review the dbGaP Tutorial on [renewals](#).

Submitting Data in the RADx Data Hub

I have new datasets/documents to add to my study. How can I add these?

Click **Data Submission** in the navigation bar's Data Submitter dropdown. This will bring you to the Data Submitter dashboard. Once there, click + **New Submission**, and follow the prompts.

How can I replace datasets/documents?

Note: The system automatically versions files. Be sure that the file you are uploading has the exact same name as the one you are replacing. Otherwise, the system will fail to create a new version and replace the file. Do not put "v.1" or any version information in the file name.

To upload a new version, go to the Data Submission dashboard and start a new submission. On step one, be sure to upload a file with the exact same name as the one you plan on replacing and continue through the prompts in the workflow. In the Review and **Submit** step, you will be able to verify whether the upload will create a new version of your files. If all is correct, press Submit, and the files will be sent to our data curation team for review. If there are no errors, the new files will replace your previous files in the system.

Can I edit study metadata in the RADx Data Hub?

After registration, you cannot edit RADx Data Hub study metadata directly in the system. To edit your metadata, please contact RADx-DataHub@nih.gov.

I have a study stored in the RADx Data Hub, but one of my study participants withdrew their consent. How do I remove the participant from the study data?

If a participant withdraws their consent, contact RADx-DataHub@nih.gov at your earliest convenience. We will remove the entire study dataset. You will need to provide revised study data, with the participant redacted, to replace your original submission. We will notify any data recipients of the situation when the redacted data are available.